

Inorganic matter partitioning in boilers with grate burners and rated output below 25 kW: Ash type and particle forming elements

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ABSTRACT

The inorganic matter of solid biofuels can be categorized into three different ash types: type-S (Si, Al, Fe, Ti), type-K (K, Na, P, Cl, S) and type-C (Ca, Mg, Mn). A total of 9 different biofuels (3 for each ash type) has been analyzed and then combusted in a 25 kW grate fired boiler. Emission factors and partitioning of typical particle forming elements (Ca, K, Na, P and Zn) were determined and show a strong correlation ($R^2 = 0.88$) with their content in the feedstock. Additionally, gaseous emissions, particle size distribution and emission factors of other major and trace elements were also established. The total ash content of the tested biofuels varied from 0.4 % for spruce up to 32.9 % for paper, however most fuels contained between 5 and 10 %. The emission factors show that the most prevalent element in the flue gas was K (generally contributing over 25 % to total particulate emissions). The release of K into the flue gas varied, with type-K fuels reaching values over 10 %, while type-S fuels only around 6 %, most likely due to the formation of refractory aluminosilicate phases. Moreover, with growing K release, the particle size distribution gradually shifted from 0.14 μm to 0.59 μm .

1. Introduction

Inorganic matter is a major cause of both technical [1,2] and environmental [3,4] problems in solid biofuel combustion. Most of the recent research has been carried out in either laboratory conditions or on industrial or district heating boilers. The extensive lab-scale works of Chen [5], Zhou [6] Van Lith [7], Pedersen [8], Knudsen [9], Frandsen [10], Ma [11], Sui et al. [12] and many others illustrate the basic principles of inorganic matter behavior. Analyses of bottom and fly ash samples collected from multiple industrial boilers by Chen et al. [13] for coal, Pei et al. [14] for wood and Ma et al. [15] for various straws further expand upon these findings.

However, case studies conducted by Kortelainen et al. [16], Adam et al. [17], Rabbat et al. [18] and others have demonstrated that the combustion conditions in small-scale boilers are vastly different. Automatic pellet boilers are common in household heating and their contribution to reducing CO₂ emissions cannot be neglected. Over time,

feedstock other than wood has been considered and at times successfully implemented [19–23]. Non-woody biomass presents a cheap and available energy source. It includes various agricultural residues, fast-growing energy plants and other organic residues. Understanding inorganic matter partitioning in small-scale boilers firing various solid biofuels is thus of great importance [24].

Vassilev et al. [25–27] conducted extensive work analyzing the inorganic composition of over 80 biomass samples and classified them based on their most abundant inorganic species into an SCK ternary diagram. The individual ash types are as follows: type-S (Si, Al, Fe, Ti), type-C (Ca, Mg, Mn), type-K (K, Na, P, Cl, S) and transitional type-CK. Multiple similarities in origin, mineral composition, combustion behavior, ash utilization etc. can be observed for fuels of each group. The environmental implications of each ash type in residential heating are thoroughly explored in the present study. During combustion, inorganic constituents remain within ash, form fouling deposits inside the boiler or in some cases are emitted from the stack. Since small-scale boilers are

Abbreviations: A^d, ash content (dry basis); AMA, atomic absorption spectroscopy; C^d, fixed carbon (dry basis); D50, cutoff diameter; daf, dry ash-free; DLPI+, Dekati low pressure impactor; EDX, electron dispersive x-ray spectroscopy; EF, emission factor; FID, flame ionization detector; ICP-MS, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry; ICP-OES, inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry; LHV, lower heating value; ME, major elements; MSW, municipal solid waste; NDIR, nondispersive infrared sensor; PM, particulate matter; PMA, paramagnetic oxygen analyzer; RSD, relative standard deviation; SCK diagram, ternary diagram of inorganic composition; SD, standard deviation; TE, trace elements; TOC, total organic carbon; V^d, volatile matter (dry basis); W^r, moisture (raw fuel); WS/SS, wood sawdust / sewage sludge.

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often equipped with no flue gas cleaning systems, their particulate matter (PM) emissions are of great environmental concern [28,29].

The transport mechanism of the various inorganic constituents to the stack can be either thermochemical or mechanical. In the thermochemical route, inorganic matter first undergoes a series of transformations, which ultimately lead to it being released as inorganic vapors. As the flue gas temperature is being brought down throughout the boiler, these vapors begin to condense on heat exchange surfaces or on solid particles. The least volatile of these can also form primary PM through homogenous nucleation. Chlorides and sulfides of various metals (Na, K, Pb, Zn) are the most common examples of particles originating from this mechanism [30–32,34]. For woody and herbaceous biomass, Kleinhans et al. [33] estimates the amount of vaporizable (particle forming) elements to be anywhere between 15 and 55 wt% of total inorganics. These vaporizable elements produce mostly ultrafine or fine particles (below 2.5 μm) [34,35]. For feedstock rich in Si, the amount of vaporizable elements can be significantly lower [33]. Mechanical transportation, on the other hand, is the physical entrainment of solid particles directly from the burner given high enough flue gas velocities and inertia. Virtually any component of the feedstock can reach the stack this way (unburnt carbon, refractory minerals etc.). These particles are generally referred to as fly-ash or coarse particles (above 2.5 μm), and according to Yang et al. [34] typically consist of Si, Ca and a smaller proportion of Al, K, P, Mg and Cl.

Small-scale boilers are often similar in design and results obtained on one appliance can, under similar enough conditions, be replicable on another. The main differences between combustion in small-scale boilers often come from the burner. However, only a handful of burner types can be found on the market: rotary burners, bottom-feed burners, drop-down burners and variations of grate burners. This initial study was conducted on 25 kW grate burner, and the results and conclusions of the study are thus applicable to small-scale boilers with the following constraints:

- the boiler is equipped with grate burner with a maximal power output of 25 kW,
- the air supply is directed solely to the burner and air staging only occurs inside the burner (no air supply nozzles are located further up the combustion chamber),
- the burner is operated within 8 and 11 % excess oxygen,
- the heating water enters the boiler at 60 °C and exits at around 80 °C,
- the combustion chamber is equipped with firebrick cladding,
- the average flue gas velocity at the stack is below 2 m/s.

The conditions specified above are derived from industry practice for small-scale boilers, technical standards (such as EN ISO 303-5 [36]), recommendations by burner and boiler suppliers and manufacturers and from previous findings of the research team [37–39] and other authors [21,40,41]. The results obtained under these conditions should be representative of a broad scale of similar heating appliances. Given the constraints and based on previous findings, two main assumptions can be made:

- under comparable combustion conditions the inorganic matter emissions and partitioning stem solely from the inorganic composition of the feedstock,
- the vast majority of inorganic matter that reaches the stack is transported through the thermochemical route described above and should therefore exclude coarse particles.

With these assumptions and under the specified conditions, the combustion behavior and inorganic matter partitioning for various biofuels, representative of the three main ash types, were studied. The research aimed to bring the extensive laboratory work of previous studies and empirical findings derived from industrial boilers to small-scale heating appliances in a systematic manner. Emission factors for

major and trace elements were established and linked with the individual ash types. Furthermore, the partitioning of particle forming elements was studied. Their content in the feedstock was also linked to their emissions to the stack. Finally, particle size distribution was determined to fully characterize particles emitted from the tested herbaceous biofuels. The study thus provides novel insight into the emission characteristics of inorganic matter fired in small-scale heating appliances.

2. Materials and methods

The experimental portion of the work encompasses a broad range of preliminary analyses to classify the different biofuels, combustion tests and emission measurement on an automatic pellet boiler and the subsequent analyses of PM and ash samples. The experimental procedure is described in detail in the following sections.

2.1. Biofuels and their classification

A sample of 9 different biofuels was collected for the experiment, comprising a wide selection of biomass; **spruce** [37] as the referential fuel, a mixture of 10 % sewage sludge and 90 % wood sawdust (**WS/SS 90/10**) [38], a variety of agricultural residues (**wheat** [39], **maize** [37] and two different kinds of **sunflower** [37,39]) in the form of husks, hulls and shells, **digestate** as the solid residue from a biogas station with feedstock mostly made of maize and cow dung, **miscanthus giganteus** as a promising energy crop and **paper** residues (clippings, inked paper cutouts etc.) from a paper-processing plant. The mixture of SS and WS was chosen due to high ash content (42.1 %) and low LHV of raw SS, which prohibit its sole combustion in the appliance. Despite SS contributing only 10 % to the mixture, its high ash content makes it the main originator of inorganic matter. The 10 % ratio was chosen based on previous experience [38]. The biofuels were either delivered or manufactured on-site in the form of 6 and 8 mm pellets. The general fuel classification was carried out in accordance with European standards EN ISO 18122 [42], EN ISO 18123 [43], EN ISO 18134-3 [44], EN ISO 18125 [45], EN ISO 16994 [46] and is presented in Table 1. The elemental composition was determined with a CHNOS Elemental analyzer. The content of volatiles (V^d) and fixed carbon (C_f^d) in paper could not be determined due to high presence of carbonates in its ash.

The inorganic composition was established in accordance with standards EN 720105-1 [47], EN 15410 [48], EN 15411 [49], and is presented graphically in Fig. 1. For the content of individual components, the reader is referred to Appendix A. Based on their position in the ternary diagram, the fuels were grouped as follows: type-C (spruce, paper, digestate), type-S (WS/SS, miscanthus, maize), type-K/CK (sunflower, sunflower 2 and wheat). For the purposes of this study, type-K and type-CK were grouped together due to their similarities.

2.2. Boiler system and burner characteristics

The tests and emission measurements were carried out on a 5-pass boiler system (Ekoscroll Alfa Pellet), shown in Fig. 2, equipped with an automatic pellet grate burner mounted from the side. The first pass, the combustion chamber, consists of an ash-pit at the bottom, the burner outlet and a firebrick lining above. The four remaining convective passes have a rectangular cross section. The third and fourth pass are equipped with turbulators to promote turbulent flow and increase heat extraction. The boiler outlet and the stack have a circular cross section with a diameter of 150 mm and are covered in thermal insulation. The sampling point is located 1100 mm above the outlet to make sure the flue gas reaches stable flow before the PM sample is isokinetically withdrawn from the stack.

The flue gas temperature was recorded at four points: thermocouple T1 was installed directly above the burner outlet (right before the flue gas enters the firebrick lining), T2 at the end of the firebrick lining, T3

Table 1
Proximate and ultimate analysis of the 9 biofuels used for the experiment.

	LHV	W ^f	A ^d	V ^d	C _f ^d	C ^{daf}	H ^{daf}	N ^{daf}	O ^{daf}	S ^{daf}	C _l ^{daf}
	MJ/kg	wt%									
spruce	16.1	7.3	0.4	84.2	15.4	49.7	7.3	0.0	43.0	0.00	0.00
paper	12.6	4.6	32.9	n.a.	n.a.	53.3	6.8	0.4	39.4	0.00	0.03
digestate	14.2	8.9	13.8	67.2	18.9	48.7	6.2	2.5	37.4	5.13	0.50
WS/SS 90/10	16.2	9.0	4.6	51.3	8.3	51.9	8.8	7.7	29.3	2.30	0.10
miscanthus	15.6	8.9	2.3	83.5	14.2	49.1	6.9	0.2	43.8	0.03	0.15
maize	15.4	8.8	6.8	78.1	15.1	48.9	7.8	2.0	41.1	0.14	0.13
sunflower	16.0	11.5	9.0	74.9	16.1	52.7	7.7	2.1	37.3	0.30	0.01
sunflower 2	17.0	7.9	5.2	75.7	19.1	51.5	6.9	1.5	39.7	0.26	0.10
wheat	16.6	10.9	5.1	77.9	17.1	50.9	7.0	2.7	39.0	0.26	0.11

Fig. 1. Ternary diagram showing the inorganic composition of the 9 biofuels.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the five-pass boiler system with a sideways mounted grate burner.

between the third and fourth pass and T4 at the stack sampling point. The T1 value should thus represent the temperature inside the combustion chamber. The actual adiabatic flame temperature is naturally

higher.

The boiler walls are cooled with heating water in the typical range of 60 °C at the inlet and around 80 °C at the outlet. The burner power output is rated 25 kW for spruce pellets. To compensate for fuels with high ash content, the boiler was operated at around 20 kW or as close to this value as each fuel allowed. The temperatures, power output and flue gas composition were all measured and recorded in real time. The flue gas composition was measured by a multi-component gas analyzer Horiba VA-5000 series. The analyzer is equipped with NDIR sensors for monitoring CO, SO₂ and NO_x (reported collectively as NO₂) concentrations, FID (flame ionization detector) for monitoring TOC (total organic carbon) concentrations and a PMA (paramagnetic oxygen analyzer) sensor for monitoring O₂ concentrations. The analyzer measures gas concentrations in dry flue gas at approximately normal conditions (prior to analysis by NDIR and PMA, the gas sample is cooled to around 4 °C and all moisture is removed). All the emission values in this study are presented in the form of emission factors described in 2.5.

2.3. Inorganic matter sampling

Upon reaching stable boiler operation in accordance with EN ISO 303-5 [36], a 2-h sampling window was initiated. An example of a

complete experimental test run is shown in Appendix A. The entire sampling procedure is illustrated in Fig. 3 and included PM collection on quartz microfiber filters (Ahlstrom-Munksjö Grade T293), inorganic vapor absorption in oxidizing solutions and bottom ash sampling. Each sample of bottom ash taken out of the ash-pit was stored in an air-proof container until it reached ambient temperature.

The PM sampling was conducted in accordance with EN 13284–1 [50]. A total of 6 filters were collected per experiment. The filters were collected concurrently in pairs, as the stack is equipped with two sampling points (shown in Fig. 4). Sampling point 1 was, in accordance with EN 14385 [51], equipped with a series of impingers containing $H_2O_2 + HNO_3$. The filters and solutions were subsequently analyzed through ICP-OES/ICP-MS to determine the contents of various major and trace elements. Sampling point 2 was, in accordance with EN 13211 [52], equipped with a series of impingers containing a solution $KMnO_4$ and H_2SO_4 and was used solely to determine the concentration of Hg through AMA analysis. The second sampling point was also used to determine PM size distribution with a Dekati cascade impactor (Dekati DLPI+). Coated aluminum substrates were used to increase collection efficiency. The third filter taken from sampling point 2 was used to determine PM elemental composition with an electron dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDX) analyzer (FIB-SEM TESCAN LYRA 3). The EDX analysis was mainly used to determine approximate C, O, Cl and S content. For the remaining elements, ICP-OES/ICP-MS was, due to its precision, the primary method of determination.

2.4. Sample analysis

The PM samples labelled ICP in Fig. 3 (filters and H_2O_2 solution) and the ash samples were analyzed on a Spectro ARCOS ICP-OES analyzer to determine the content of major elements (ME): Al, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Na, P, Ti and Zn. The solid samples were mineralized prior to the analysis in accordance with standard EN 14385 [51]. The standard detection limit for a 100 mg solid sample (all the ash samples and most filters) is 15 ppm. For filters with lower collected mass (especially spruce and type-S fuels), the detection limit linearly increased. The relative expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of the analysis was in all cases below 20 %. For trace element (TE) analysis ICP-MS equipped with He collision cell (Agilent 7500, Agilent, USA) was used. The detection limits for the trace elements were 5 ppm (Mn), 0.1 ppm (As), 0.05 ppm (Co, Cr, V, Ni, Sb), 0.008 ppm (Pb, Cd), and 0.001 ppm (Tl). The PM samples labelled AMA and the $KMnO_4$ solution were analyzed through atomic absorption spectroscopy on AMA 254 analyzer (Altec, Prague). The standard detection limits for a 20 mg solid sample and 0.25 ml solution are 1 and 0.1 ppb, respectively.

2.5. Inorganic matter emission factor and partitioning

In the context of this study, the emission factor (EF) quantifies the

amount of pollutant/element (mg or μg) released per 1 kg of burnt fuel. We differentiate between two EF values: EF_i^{fg} is the amount of pollutant/element released to flue gas, whereas EF_i^{ash} is the amount of element retained in bottom ash. The former is used to describe actual emissions from the boiler, while the latter primarily serves to determine elemental partitioning between the two pathways. The following procedure describes the determination of EF_i^{fg} for any given ME or TE. The same approach was used to determine the gaseous and total PM EF values (Table 2). To establish the value of EF_i^{fg} , the measured concentrations of individual elements in the flue gas were first referenced to 0 % oxygen content according to Eq. (1) adopted from standard EN ISO 303-5 [36]:

$$C_{N,d}^{\alpha=1} = C_{N,d} \cdot \frac{21 - 0}{21 - O_{2,avg}} \quad (mg/Nm^3) \quad (1)$$

where $C_{N,d}$ (mg/Nm^3) is the measured concentration of any given element in dry flue gas at normal conditions and $O_{2,avg}$ (%) is the average volumetric concentration of oxygen in the filter sampling window. The emission factor is then given by:

$$EF_i^{fg} = C_{N,d}^{\alpha=1} \cdot O_{fg,min,d} \quad (mg/kg_{fuel}) \quad (2)$$

where $O_{fg,min,d}$ (Nm^3/kg_{fuel}) is the theoretical stoichiometric amount of dry flue gas released from 1 kg of burnt fuel (see Appendix A). This value is based solely on the elemental composition of the fuel (Table 1) and assumes ideal and complete combustion.

The EF_i^{ash} (mg/kg_{fuel}) represents the amount of a particular element retained in bottom ash and was determined according to:

$$EF_i^{ash} = C_i^{ash} \cdot A^r \quad (mg/kg_{fuel}) \quad (3)$$

where C_i^{ash} (mg/kg_{fuel}) is the concentration of any given element in the ash sample and A^r (kg_{ash}/kg_{fuel}) is the ash content of the corresponding fuel (taken from Table 1). Finally, combining the two EF values, we can determine RR_i (%) or the relative release of each element into the flue gas:

$$RR_i = \frac{EF_i^{fg}}{EF_i^{fg} + EF_i^{ash}} \quad (-) \quad (4)$$

The value of RR presented in Fig. 6 was established from the average values of EF_i^{fg} and EF_i^{ash} for each fuel/element.

Fig. 3. PM and ash sampling procedure upon reaching stable operating conditions.

Fig. 4. Schematic of the two flue gas sampling points.

Table 2

Average power output, gaseous and total PM emissions, O₂ concentration and flue gas temperatures for each fuel (SD – standard deviation, RSD – relative standard deviation).

	power output	NO _x	CO	TOC	SO ₂	PM	O ₂	T1	T2	T3	T4
	kW	mg/kg _{fuel}					vol%	°C			
spruce	19.1	1240	4177	14	138	295	9.4	773	408	232	127
paper	16.0	1345	4786	89	264	236	10.0	571	351	201	111
digestate	20.6	4674	1461	305	7288	8862	9.0	775	451	249	139
WS/SS 90/10	20.7	4006	688	2	2110	693	10.9	693	414	249	148
miscanthus	15.9	2457	718	15	636	633	8.4	756	427	226	125
maize	18.8	5770	1744	27	924	1413	9.6	779	485	259	141
sunflower	19.2	4352	7460	44	315	2732	8.4	836	483	254	136
sunflower 2	19.9	4102	18,554	128	340	4414	10.4	840	507	251	130
wheat	20.0	5971	451	45	2580	2865	9.1	794	440	249	141
SD	1.8						0.79	77.6	45.0	17.3	10.5
RSD	9.5 %						8.4 %	10.3 %	10.2 %	7.2 %	7.9 %

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Process conditions and fuel behavior

The process conditions listed in Table 2 represent the average values throughout the necessary sampling procedure. To accommodate comparable combustion conditions for all fuels, it was imperative to minimize deviations between the main process conditions: power output, O₂ concentration and temperatures T1 to T4. These deviations are represented by the relative standard deviation (RSD) presented in Table 2. Since the RSD was in all cases around 10 % or below, the comparability

of the conditions was deemed satisfactory. The most prominent outliers in terms of power output were miscanthus and paper, both at around 16 kW. Incomplete fuel burnout prohibited higher fuel throughput for miscanthus (see Appendix A). The high ash content of paper (32.9 %) hindered heat retention in the burner, and the power output also had to be decreased accordingly. This also manifested in the lowest flue gas temperatures among all fuels. The average power output for the remaining fuels was around the desired 19–20 kW.

O₂ concentrations in the flue gas are directly proportional to the amount of air/fuel supplied to the burner. Air/fuel ratio is among the most important factors when it comes to inorganic matter partitioning.

Fig. 5. The combustion characteristics of type-K/CK fuels (top row) and type-S fuels (bottom row), from left: the ash pit / burner outlet, the entry to the second pass from the firebrick lining, quartz filters with PM deposits.

Since the RSD for O₂ concentration was 8.4 %, it is highly likely that most differences in inorganic matter partitioning stem from the fuel composition and not air/fuel ratio.

The combustion behavior was consistent among fuels with similar inorganic composition. Type-S fuels were prone to severe slagging and produced thin soot/mineral deposits in the first pass (see Fig. 5). Coarse fly ash particles were found only in the firebrick lining. Fouling deposits in the four convective passes were minimal. The deposits were similar to those of type-C fuels. The PM collected on the filters was black or grey in color, indicating high soot / low KCl emissions. After the initial slag formation, a sharp decrease in CO emissions was observed for all type-S fuels. This could most likely be attributed to even air distribution through the porous slag. The slag, however, had to be manually removed from the burner after the sampling concluded, to prevent the burner from clogging.

Type-K/CK fuels produced soft, flocculent ash that was easily disposed of by the grate reciprocating motion. Due to the high content of inorganic volatiles, the combustion of these fuels released significant amounts of inorganic vapors. Since the flue gas temperature decreased sharply in the first pass (on average to 440 °C), the vapors began to condense on the last row of firebricks, forming white deposits (Fig. 5) made of mostly potassium salt deposits. The condensation would continue throughout the remaining boiler passes, promoted by the relatively low wall temperature. Similar white deposits formed on the quartz filter when extracting stack gases for PM sampling. For the same amount of burnt fuel, the type-K/CK fuels formed considerably thicker deposits than type-S or type-C fuels. However, both types of deposits were easily removed with manual scraping. Due to their water solubility, the type-K/CK deposits could possibly be effectively removed by periodic water flushing.

3.2. Inorganic matter EFs to the flue gas

The inorganic matter EFs shown in Table 3 represent the combined (filters + vapors) average values determined from the samples labelled

ICP and SEM in Fig. 3. For each fuel, the individual elements have been ranked from most abundant (green) to least (red). The most abundant inorganic constituents found in flue gas were in decreasing order C, K, P, Na, Zn, Ca. Carbon in the flue gas is generally present as soot and tars (or similar organic compounds). The emissions of soot and tars are typically proportional to CO and TOC emissions [53]; and as such the lowest carbon EFs were also observed for fuels with low CO and TOC EFs. The nature of carbon in PM can also be estimated from these values e.g. for spruce, the carbon EF was 75.9 mg/kg_{fuel} and the CO and TOC EFs 4177 mg/kg_{fuel} and 14 mg/kg_{fuel}, respectively. Since the CO EF is significantly higher than that of TOC, it can be concluded that most carbon present on the spruce PM is in the form of soot. On the other hand, the total carbon EF for digestate was at 775.3 mg/kg_{fuel} the highest of all fuels. Its CO EF was, however, three times lower than for spruce, while its TOC EF was more than six times higher. It can thus be assumed that most carbon present on digestate PM was in the form of organic compounds. Low carbon EFs were observed for both type-C and type-S fuels with the only exception being digestate due to its high TOC emissions.

Cl, S and O present on PM are generally in the form of bearing compounds of the other inorganic constituents, i.e. as chlorides, sulfides or oxides of K, Na, P, Zn etc. Oxygen may also be present in organic compounds with carbon or as carbonates. Of the two main bearing compounds (chlorides and sulfides/sulfates), Cl seems to be the more common in most cases, with the only exception being sunflower 2, where the sulfur EF exceeds that of Cl by 197 mg/kg_{fuel}. Chlorine EFs also show significantly stronger correlation with potassium EF (*R* = 0.97) compared to sulfur (*R* = 0.79). It can thus be assumed that the majority of K released to the flue gas was in the form of chlorides.

According to Gollmer et al. [29] the feedstock composition affects K speciation, which can be volatilized as gaseous KOH, KCl, K₂SO₄, K₂CO₃ or K₃PO₄. Yang et al. [35] mentions that K-phosphates exist in different forms in ultrafine and fine particle, mainly in the form of K₃PO₄ in fine particles, and in the form of KPO₃ in ultrafine particles. The fuels with the lowest chlorine and sulfur EFs also show the lowest potassium EFs. P, Zn, Na and Ca generally contribute little to the total PM emissions, the

Table 3
Average EFs of ME to flue gas and their linear correlation with total PM EF (mg/kg_{fuel}) with SD for *n* = 3.

										of total PM	
	spruce	paper	digestate	WS/SS 90/10	miscanthus	maize	sunflower	sunflower 2	wheat		correlation with total PM
C	75.9 ± 6.1	24.5 ± 1.2	775.3 ± 93	154.1 ± 13.9	136.6 ± 15	331.7 ± 33.2	310 ± 15.5	500.8 ± 30	496.3 ± 39.7		0.94
O	60.2 ± 1.2	36.8 ± 1.8	3212 ± 96.4	237.1 ± 11.9	182.5 ± 11	214.3 ± 12.9	599.3 ± 24	1591.5 ± 79.6	396.9 ± 55.6		0.98
S	15.2 ± 0.6	2.8 ± 0.3	385.1 ± 27	5.2 ± 0.8	18.1 ± 0.7	26.8 ± 1.3	222.8 ± 6.7	614.6 ± 18.4	84.6 ± 14.4		0.76
Cl	17.1 ± 2.6	7.8 ± 1.6	1050 ± 52.5	1.5 ± 0	101.1 ± 2	228.2 ± 6.8	365.9 ± 7.3	417.5 ± 37.6	414.5 ± 53.9		0.98
Al	0.3 ± 0.1	3.2 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0	1.3 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.012	0.3 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0	0.9 ± 0.4		-0.07
Ca	7.1 ± 1.7	42.4 ± 1.3	7.5 ± 3.2	11.7 ± 0.8	3.1 ± 0.7	20.9 ± 2.5	11.9 ± 8.4	12.2 ± 0.9	8.6 ± 1.3		-0.30
Fe	1.5 ± 0.9	9.2 ± 0.6	4.9 ± 0.1	2.8 ± 0.5	15.5 ± 11.8	1.8 ± 0.5	3.9 ± 1.5	2.5 ± 1.3	10.4 ± 9.2		-0.16
K	105.6 ± 40.1	65.1 ± 7.2	2202 ± 110.1	72.5 ± 3.6	115.1 ± 5.8	502 ± 20.1	1112.6 ± 66.8	1225.4 ± 49	711.8 ± 64.1		0.98
Mg	1.1 ± 0.2	1.5 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.4	2.3 ± 0.2	1.5 ± 0.2	39.5 ± 2.4	4 ± 2.2	3.8 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.1		-0.12
Na	4.1 ± 1.2	22.3 ± 2	368.6 ± 18.4	13 ± 1.3	5.4 ± 0.3	14.9 ± 1.3	11.9 ± 0.5	11 ± 0.7	8.2 ± 0		0.86
P	0.7 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.1	792.4 ± 87.2	136.7 ± 5.5	34.2 ± 0.3	3 ± 0.6	2.7 ± 0.1	21.2 ± 0.6	314.3 ± 28.3		0.84
Ti	0 ± 0	0.1 ± 0	0 ± 0	0.1 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	0 ± 0		-0.41
Zn	4.3 ± 3.2	11.5 ± 0.5	51.1 ± 1.5	47.8 ± 1	12.9 ± 2.5	9.7 ± 1.5	14.9 ± 3	10.2 ± 0	78.5 ± 41.6		0.40
Total PM	295 ± 14	236 ± 22	8862 ± 549	693 ± 43	633 ± 45	1413 ± 71	2732 ± 191	4414 ± 40	2865 ± 289		

only exceptions being WS/SS, digestate and wheat for P, digestate and paper for Na, paper for Ca and WS/SS for Zn. Yang et al. [35] report that the combustion of SS is usually accompanied by high P emissions, in the form of K_3PO_4 or KPO_3 . The release and partitioning of P, Na and Ca is further discussed below. Al, Fe, Mg and Ti (all type-S constituents) are among the least volatile and are generally present in refractory phases. As such their contribution to PM emissions is minimal and mostly limited to coarse fly ash. The results for spruce are in line with what has previously been reported by Rabbat et al. [18] or Wiinikka et al. [54] and confirm the validity of the methodology deployed in the present study. Other authors similarly report that PM_{10} particles from firing wood in a variety of appliances are dominated by K (to a lesser extent Cl and S) and the prominence of Ca in PM only rises with increasing aerodynamic diameter (above 1 μm) [55–58]. Since the aerodynamic diameter of the PM in the present study did not significantly exceed 1 μm (see Table 4), the contribution of Ca to PM EF is minor. Comparative data for herbaceous biomass is scarce, however, in a lab-scale study Yang et al. [59] confirm that for cornstalk pellets, the elemental distribution is similar to that of wood. In another study [60] conducted on the same apparatus on cotton stalk, corn stalk and rice husks PM_{10} particles were found to be mostly made of K, Cl and Na, while Ca and Mg were found solely on coarse particles. Based on the results of the present study, it can be stated that P can, in some cases, also contribute significantly to PM_{10} emissions.

3.3. Inorganic matter partitioning

The inorganic matter partitioning is illustrated in Fig. 6 in the form of relative release. The percentages present the degree to which each element has been released from the boiler and through the stack. Coarse fly ash retained in the boiler and fouling deposits have been excluded. It is clear from Table 3 that the most prominent inorganic constituent in the flue gas is potassium. Type-C fuels show the largest disparity, ranging from around 5 % for paper (65.1 mg/kg_{fuel}) to 20 % for digestate (2202 mg/kg_{fuel}) and 25 % for spruce (105.6 mg/kg_{fuel}). On the other hand, K release from type-S fuels is more consistent (between 4 and 8 %). Similarly, type-K/CK fuels, ranked among the highest in terms of K emissions, show a narrow range of K release (between 10 and 14 %). In their study on a 500 kW boiler Sippula et al. [57] reported that the addition of peat (type-S fuel) to wood helps retain K in bottom-ash. Van Lith et al. [7] observed similar behavior in a lab-scale drop tube furnace. As such, type-S fuels uniformly exhibit the lowest release of K. Na shows similar behavior to K, albeit its contribution to total PM emissions is much lower. The release of Na for both type-S and type-K/CK fuels is consistent, ranging from 4.6 to 7.3 %.

Of all the particle-forming elements, Ca overall demonstrated the lowest mobility. Its release has not surpassed 1 % for any of the tested fuels. The Ca content in the feedstock varied widely; with paper at 38300 mg/kg_{fuel} and spruce at 342 mg/kg_{fuel}. It would thus seem that in the case of small-scale boilers, PM emissions are not at all proportional to the amount of Ca in the feedstock. The contribution of Zn to total PM emissions was, for different fuels, similar to that of Ca. Its mobility, however, was the highest of all particle-forming elements, generally ranging from 60 to almost 90 %, apart from paper at 30 %. In their study, Magiera et al. [61] mention that fine dust from coniferous wood was significantly enriched in Zn. Ma et al. [11] report that at temperatures over 1250 °C around 95 % of Zn was released to flue gas for various biofuels. Co-firing them with coal slime (type-S fuel) did not increase Zn retention in bottom ash. Even for coal (type-S fuel), Zn is often ranked among the most volatile elements [13]. Finally, P showed the largest variation, ranging from almost negligible release to up to 9 % for miscanthus. Despite this, the correlation between P and total PM emissions was relatively strong ($R = 0.84$, see Table 3).

Overall, spruce showed significantly higher release of Ca, K and Na than any other tested fuel. Due to its low ash content, however, this amounted to relatively low total PM emissions (295 mg/kg_{fuel}). Conversely, the release of all elements was the lowest for paper, regardless of its high ash content. The correlation between the release of each element and the Cl and S content in the feedstock was also tested. The results are, however, nonconclusive, as the only element that showed moderate correlation with Cl content in the feedstock was P ($R = 0.57$).

3.4. PM size distribution

The PM size distribution presented in Table 4 clearly indicates that the majority of emitted PM does not reach equivalent aerodynamic diameter over 1 μm . Coarse fly ash thus almost entirely remains within the boiler; in the ash pit, firebrick lining or as deposits on boiler walls. As such, the main bulk of PM that is released through the stack undergoes the thermochemical route, i.e. is released as vapors that nucleate or condense on already formed soot or inorganic particles. The order of the fuels in Table 4 has been changed to demonstrate the growing tendency of peak contributions. The two fuels with the lowest overall PM emissions, spruce and paper (both type-C) reached peak particle emissions at 0.14 μm . All type-S fuels reached peak particle emissions slightly above, at 0.25 μm . The peak size began to shift again for the type-K/CK fuels to 0.37 μm , and ultimately to 0.59 μm for digestate. It appears that with growing K release and emissions, the PM size gradually increases as well,

Table 4
PM size distribution reported as emission factors for varying D50 (mg/kg_{fuel}).

		<0.1%	0.1-0.5%	0.5-1.5%	1.5-4%	4-7%	7-25%	25-42%	of total PM						
D50 (μm)		0.013	0.028	0.05	0.09	0.14	0.25	0.37	0.59	0.94	1.62	2.46	3.65	5.37	9.89
spruce	C	0.4	1.1	6.7	44.3	76.7	50.8	13.1	3.9	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.3
paper	C	2.8	4.9	10.4	44.4	90.9	45.3	12.5	8.3	10.9	1.4	4.2	5.6	9.0	9.0
WS/SS 90/10	S	23.4	20.7	5.7	20.1	54.6	126.7	45.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	5.3
miscanthus	S	1.2	6.0	15.7	33.7	86.9	121.3	28.5	9.0	3.7	0.0	7.5	2.6	3.0	8.9
maize	S	0.0	15.0	42.9	73.9	365.4	691.9	361.4	77.9	30.9	12.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	52.9
sunflower 2	CK	20.8	11.6	43.9	81.0	323.8	942.5	1016.5	321.5	88.2	17.3	4.6	11.6	0.0	13.9
wheat	K	6.6	15.9	10.4	25.9	94.5	477.7	399.9	278.9	98.0	1.2	3.5	4.0	0.0	4.0
sunflower	CK	9.6	13.0	25.9	62.5	269.4	848.0	1113.1	321.1	116.4	30.2	9.7	3.2	9.7	24.8
digestate	C	25.5	11.5	21.3	43.5	125.8	657.7	1563.1	1525.6	1113.8	96.8	8.9	7.1	2.7	17.8

Fig. 6. Relative release of typical particle forming elements into the flue gas (reported in rel.%) with SD for $n = 3$.

however not over 1 μm . While coarse PM has been detected for each fuel, its contribution to the total PM emissions has not been as significant. Rebling et al. [62] report similar results for type-C fuels (softwood pellets and Salix chips) combusted in industrial-scale grate-fired boilers. The concentrations of emitted particles for woody biomass, in their case, peaked at 0.14–0.25 μm . Similar observations were made by Fagerström et al. [63] for forest residues fired in a 15 kW automatic pellet boiler. For type-S (rice husks) and type-K/CK fuels (cotton and corn stalk), peak concentrations were generally measured around 0.25 μm [64–66] in various combustion appliances. For wheat straw (type-K), however, the reported concentrations peaked between 0.26 and 0.37 μm [18]. Wheat straw showed, similarly to digestate in the present study, the highest PM emissions of all tested fuels. Under optimal combustion conditions, the

PM size distribution in small-scale appliances is thus generally governed by the inorganic composition of the fuel, especially its K content and release to the flue gas.

3.5. Trace elements

Apart from ME, certain hazardous TE have been measured as well. The list of the elements presented in Table 5 was chosen based on the current Czech legislation for MSW (municipal solid waste) combustion, as no emission limits for biofuels currently exist. TE that were below the detection limit (Tl, Sb, V) for all 9 fuels are excluded from the table. While biomass does generally not contain as many harmful elements as coal or municipal solid waste, some waste-derived biofuels may be

Table 5
Average EF of trace elements to flue gas ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$) with SD for $n = 3$, ND – not detected.

	spruce	paper	digestate	WS/SS 90/10	miscanthus	maize	sunflower	sunflower 2	wheat
As	ND	ND	360.4 ± 73.1	640 ± 32.3	ND	22.6 ± 7.2	ND	ND	62.6 ± 19
Cd	23.7 ± 5.9	31.3 ± 7.6	ND	95.2 ± 2.7	ND	22.3 ± 4.9	64 ± 0.9	29.6 ± 4.7	34.1 ± 6.7
Co	ND	ND	ND	ND	44 ± 28.4	2.1 ± 5.3	ND	ND	62.1 ± 27.6
Cr	237.4 ± 135.3	1526.2 ± 3.6	339.5 ± 28.1	88.8 ± 19.2	2501.2 ± 286	157.2 ± 350.2	467.8 ± 1221	274.6 ± 20.4	420 ± 75.5
Cu	172.4 ± 112.1	508 ± 42.2	333.4 ± 81.2	528.1 ± 6.1	642.5 ± 1755	1417.2 ± 134.9	477.5 ± 116.8	611.2 ± 10	2250 ± 1318
Hg	ND	ND	1.6 ± 0.2	19.5 ± 2.7	1 ± 0.3	ND	0.8 ± 0.3	0.5 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.6
Mn	1550.9 ± 124.1	1696.7 ± 215.9	ND	2698.2 ± 6.8	492.3 ± 1020	97.4 ± 64	496.7 ± 339.3	226.9 ± 67.2	1821.9 ± 17.5
Ni	27.1 ± 18.2	1100 ± 98.4	925.4 ± 378	55.3 ± 41.4	1100 ± 935	296.1 ± 165	518.8 ± 440	193.3 ± 112	1100 ± 248.7
Pb	65.6 ± 3.3	5491.1 ± 128.5	2061 ± 3.7	2141.5 ± 6.7	243.2 ± 9.3	120.1 ± 55.9	182.5 ± 439.3	222.4 ± 41.1	116.3 ± 24

problematic. If spruce is to be taken as a baseline, it is clear that for certain fuels the EFs of many elements far surpassed the EFs of spruce. WS/SS seems to be the most problematic with its high emissions of As, Cd, Hg and Pb. High Pb emissions were also measured for digestate and especially paper (at 5491 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$). Paper, paperboard, clippings and food packaging often contain excessive amounts of Pb. In a study by Elmas et al. [67] 18 various paper samples were analyzed for their Pb content, which ranged from 2 to 12.9 $\text{mg}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$. The TE content in both digestate and sewage sludge is generally variable as it largely depends on the feedstock. For instance, Derehajtó et al. [68] measured the concentration of Pb, Cd and Hg in monthly samples of digestate from maize and cow dung. Over the course of 15 months, the concentrations of Pb ranged between 2.5 and 5 $\text{mg}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$ (in one case 11 $\text{mg}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$), Cd between 0.25 and 0.4 $\text{mg}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$ (in one case 0.8 $\text{mg}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$) and Hg between 0.012 and 0.022 $\text{mg}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$. Golovko et al. [69], on the other hand, collected samples from 3 different biogas plants and found between 2 and 7.4 $\text{mg}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$ of Pb. The variation and contents of Cd were, however, significantly lower (between 0.35 and 0.37 $\text{mg}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$).

The relative release of most TE into the flue gas is difficult to estimate, due to their low concentration in the feedstock and its heterogeneous nature. It can be stated with a great degree of certainty, however, that among the most volatile trace elements were Hg, Pb and Cd, as they were identified almost exclusively in PM. The high volatility of these elements was previously reported by Zhou et al. [6], Sui et al. [12] and others [11,13,70] on various combustion appliances and for various solid fuels. The estimated release of Hg, Pb and Cd in the present study ranged from 80 to 100 %, with the lowest values being observed for all type-S fuels. Their EF to the flue gas are thus directly proportional to their content in the feedstock, as was previously noted by Sippula et al. [57] in their case study on cofiring wood and peat.

The emissions of Mn were among the highest of all the trace elements. Its release to the flue gas was, however, minimal and has not reached higher than 3.3 % in the case of paper. The low release of Mn to the flue gas was previously observed by Duan et al. [70] for coal, Kortelainen et al. [16] for wood and its blends with straw and reed canary grass and Ma et al. [11] for moso bamboo. The release of the remaining elements varied widely, and no definitive relation between the ash type and their release could be established.

3.6. Approximation based on ash type and particle forming elements

The individual ash types can be used as preliminary indicator of fuel behavior. In all instances type-S fuels produced slag and moderate amounts of PM, while type-K/CK fuels showed no slagging and produced high PM emissions. Type-C fuels showed the highest disparity in PM

emissions and no slagging, although minor clinkers were found in the ash from digestate. Contrary to type-S fuels, the digestate clinkers did not agglomerate and posed no technical difficulties. The position of the fuel in the ternary diagram (Fig. 1) can only determine the fuel behavior, but not the extent of either slagging or PM emissions. The latter can be somewhat accurately predicted by establishing the content of particle forming elements in the feedstock, as shown previously by Kuptz et al. [28].

Based on the results presented in Table 3 and Fig. 6, the particle forming elements proposed by Kleinhans et al. [33] can be reduced to Cl, S, K, Na, P and Zn in the context of small-scale boilers, as Pb contributes minimally to PM emission due to its trace concentrations in the feedstock and Ca is not released to the flue gas no matter the fuel. The relation between the content of these six elements in the feedstock and total inorganic matter emissions at the stack (total PM excluding carbon and oxygen) is shown in Fig. 7. The relation shows a strong linear correlation ($R^2 = 0.88$) if digestate is excluded. The exclusion of digestate was indicated purely by statistical means (identifying it as an outlier). Its atypical behavior can be attributed to many compounding factors (high Cl content and P release, reducing conditions due to excessive emissions of TOC, the presence of more mobile phases due to biological degradation during fermentation etc.). However, based on the available data, it is impossible to determine the underlying thermochemical cause for its outlier status. The correlation thus applies favorably to type-S and type-K/CK fuels. While spruce and paper (type-C) fuels follow the correlation as well, digestate remains a strong outlier.

4. Conclusions

The conclusions of the study apply to grate-fired boilers up to 25 kW or equipped with a similarly rated and designed burner, where forced air supply is directed from below the fuel bed (drop-down and retort burners) and no over-fire air supply is present. The boiler should also be operated at the typical conditions of 60/80 °C water temperature, 8–11 % O_2 content in the flue gas and 12 Pa draft (< 2 m/s stack velocity) and equipped with firebrick cladding in the furnace. In such instances, the following conclusions should be applicable:

- Potassium, in its various forms, is the main contributor to inorganic PM emissions. Other constituents include Na, P, Zn and Ca.
- Type-K and type-CK fuels show almost identical behavior and can be grouped together.
- Type-S fuels are prone to severe slagging, but produce only moderate amounts of PM, due to the formation of refractory aluminosilicates and low K release into the flue gas.

Fig. 7. The relation between particle forming elements in the feedstock and total inorganic emissions at the stack ($n = 3$).

- Type-K/CK fuels show no slagging but produce high PM emissions. The release of potassium was on average twice as high as for type-S fuels.
- Type-C fuels are the least consistent but like type-K/CK fuels show no slagging, apart from digestate which showed only minor slagging. Their PM emissions varied the most, with spruce and paper reaching the lowest values, while digestate reaching the highest.
- The content of Cl, S, K, Na, P and Zn in the feedstock can be used as a relatively accurate predictor of total inorganic PM emissions for both type-S and type-K/CK fuels. For type-C fuels, chlorine content needs to be checked separately.
- Small-scale boilers release virtually only submicron particles, no matter the inorganic composition of the feedstock. The released PM is thus formed from vapors of volatile inorganic compounds.

Future research should be carried out on similarly rated boilers with different burner characteristics (rotary burners and over-fire air supply). Operating conditions of the burner should also be examined in greater detail (such as oxygen supply, operation at reduced power output) along with the effects firebrick layout might have on the partitioning. Long term operation and the evolution of deposit formation and inorganic release should also be investigated to establish the necessary foundation. Furthermore, the deployment of additives (such as limestone, dolomite, kaolin etc.) on fuel behavior and inorganic matter release should also be determined in the context of these appliances. Finally, flue gas cleaning systems such as wet scrubbing, condensation or electrostatic precipitators, now commonly used in modern wood pellet boilers, could be tested on other solid biofuels. Some of the experimental work is already being carried out by the research team to fill these gaps, however, validation by other research groups is naturally necessary.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jakub Lachman: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Marek Balás:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Validation. **Martin Lisý:** Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Tereza Zleavorová:** Investigation, Data curation, Visualization. **Hana Lisá:** Methodology, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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The majority of the findings, results and data have been previously published in a doctoral thesis [71], written in the Czech language, by the corresponding author. Some of the data has since been expanded (Fig. 6) or further processed and analyzed to form the newly added regression analysis in Fig. 7. The remaining figures and tables contain data published in the aforementioned doctoral thesis or in the cited studies. None of the contents of this paper have, however, been previously published in a peer-reviewed journal, unless properly cited. The research was funded by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic, grant no.: TQ03000712 and by Brno University of Technology in frame of the Specific Research Fund, grant no.: FSI-S-23-8223.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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